

Symbolic Representations on the Coins of the Early Medieval Western Turkish Empire

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Abstract: This article examines the symbolic motifs present on the coins minted in Choch by the West Turkic Khanate during the early Middle Ages. Furthermore, numismatic evidence suggests that these symbols are intricately linked to the socio-political and religious-ideological contexts of the period, as well as to the prevailing state traditions and expressions of authority.

Introduction: Numismatic materials are recognized as a unique historical source that provides valuable insights into the socio-political and ethno-cultural life of their respective eras. This significance stems from the fact that coins were minted under the authority of specific ruling figures. Despite often bearing only brief inscriptions, they offer reliable and concrete information that distinguishes them from other historical sources. Over twenty distinct types of coins from the Western Khaganate of the early Middle Ages, particularly from the sixth to eighth centuries, have been identified. Nearly all of these coins feature symbolic motifs, many of which denote expressions of power, while others are associated with religious beliefs.

No	Coin type and corresponding reign, period	Symbol type and designation.	Representation of symbols.	Depiction of the coin.	Published scholarly research.
1	Coin without inscription from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch), dating from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Bow and arrow apparatuses.?			Babayar 2007: 57;
2	Titled "Jabghu," this artifact originates from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dates from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Astrological symbols: crescent and star.			Бабаяров 2007: 14;

3	Coin without inscription from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch), dating from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Fire altar.			Бабаяров 2007: 17;
4	Titled "Jabghu," this artifact originates from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dates from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Three-pointed headdresses.			Ртвеладзе 2006: 92-93; Бабаяров 2007: 14;
5	Western Turkic Khaganate (Hair), dating from the late 6th century to the early 7th century. Inscribed "Jabghu Chirdanak currency."	pregnant woman			Бабаяров 2021: 210
6	Coin without inscription from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch), dating from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Gesture of the hand.			Babayar 2007: 58;
7	Coin without inscription from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch), dating from the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Aso (staff or cane).			Бабаяров 2007: 10;
8	He holds the title of "Khagan of the Turks," originating from the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) during the late 6th century to the early 7th century.	Crescent moon.			Бабаяров. 2007: 13;

9	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.	Huma bird.?			Ртвеладзе 1982: 34-35;
10	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.	Geruda bird.			Бабаяров 2007: 9
11	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.	Zoomorphic throne design.			Ртвеладзе 1987: 167-168; Babayar 2007: 56
12	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.	Sword.			Бабаяров 2007: 10-11
13	“Элби Ишбара Сир жабгу-хоқон” унвонли. Ғарбий Турк хоқонлиги (Чоч). VII аср илк чораги	Crescent moon and full moon.			Ртвеладзе 1982: 34; Бабаяров 2007: 12; Zeno.ru#3 22638
14	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch) and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.	Cross symbol.			Ртвеладзе 1982: 38; Бабаяров 2007: 17-18
15	It is titled "Tun Jabgu-Khokan," associated with the Western Turkic Khaganate (Choch)	Dubious.			Бабаяров 2007: 19

	and dating to the first quarter of the 7th century.				
16	He holds the title of "Khakan," a designation that emerged during the latter half of the 7th century.	a camel with two humps			Бабаяров 2007: 20

Methods:

Bow and arrow apparatus. Several types of coins from the Western Turkic Khanate feature a symbolic representation of a bow and arrow. Among the ancient Turks, one enduring tradition, believed to date back to a divine origin, involved the practice of taking oaths with swords, daggers, and bows and arrows. Numismatic evidence further illustrates that the bow and arrow served as emblems of power and courage among the Turkic peoples. (Coin 1)

Crescent and star. This symbol appears exclusively on one type of coin from the Western Turkic Khanate: a double portrait coin featuring the title "jabgu." The crescent moon and star symbol is frequently encountered on the coins of pre-Islamic rulers from Central Asian oases, where it is regarded as an emblem of power. Notably, this iconography is characteristic of Parthian coins minted in Marv and later became prevalent on coins from Sasanian Iran. Ancient Central Asian peoples, particularly the ancestors of the Turkic peoples, esteemed this symbol as a celestial sign, akin to its significance among many cultures worldwide, viewing it as a representation of statehood and authority. Furthermore, the ancient Turks regarded the appearance of a new moon and a crescent moon accompanied by a bright star as auspicious, believing it to portend victory in battle. (Coin 2)

Fire altar. This imagery appears on coins from the Western Turkic Khaganate, specifically in one coin type. It suggests that the Khaganate's initial coinage was influenced by Zoroastrianism, as evidenced by the depiction of a bonfire. However, over time, the Khaganate shifted away from this influence, opting to incorporate symbols that aligned more closely with its own belief system. The representation of fire on coins from early medieval Central Asia was predominantly found in the coinage of Bukhara and Tokharistan. In contrast, such imagery is notably absent from the coins of Sughd, Ustrushona, Choch, Fergana, O'tror, and Isfijab, as well as from those of Ettisuv, where the Sogdian cultural milieu is prevalent. This divergence underscores the distinct cultural and religious influences that shaped the numismatic traditions across the region. (Coin 3)

Three-pointed headdress. Among the coins of the Western Turkic Khaganate, there is a notable prevalence of coins featuring double portraits. A prominent example of this is the depiction of a khatun (princess) wearing a three-pointed headdress alongside the khagan. This headdress carries significant symbolic meaning and is associated with the goddess Umai, who is revered as the protector of children and warriors, as well as the patroness of pregnancy and fertility. The inclusion of such imagery reflects the intertwining of political and spiritual authority within the khanate, highlighting the importance of female figures in the socio-religious landscape of the time. (Coin 4)

Pregnant woman. Among the double-portrait coins of the Western Turkic Khanate, one notable type features a ruler accompanied by his pregnant wife. This depiction is emblematic of Umay, the maternal figure revered in Turkic culture. Umay is traditionally recognized for her role in safeguarding infants from conception through birth and early childhood, providing protection against various afflictions and misfortunes. Additionally, she serves as the protector of the state's heir apparent, underscoring her significance in both maternal and political domains. (Coin 5)

Gesture of the hand. This symbol appears on the majority of coins from the Western Turkic Khanate. Across diverse cultures worldwide, many symbolic hand gestures have been preserved from ancient times

to the present. Historical artifacts from civilizations such as ancient Egypt, Rome, Greece, Iran, and India often sought to convey specific words or ideas through various representations of hand movements—whether through the hand itself or its fingers in distinct forms. This phenomenon is also evident in the visual and practical arts of Central Asia during the ancient period and the early Middle Ages. The symbol is generally interpreted to signify "God bless you" or "God is one." (Coin 6)

Aso (staff or cane). In Turkic cultures, the scepter is recognized as a significant symbol of power, a notion supported by artifacts from both the pre-Islamic Turkic dynasties and the subsequent Muslim Turkic dynasties. A notable example is a bone carving from Northern Mongolia, tentatively identified as depicting an ancient Turkish official, which vividly illustrates this symbolism. Additionally, wall paintings from the Afrosiyab palace in Samarkand, believed to have been created around 650 CE, portray an official from the ancient Turkic khanate leaning on a long staff. These representations underscore the enduring association between the scepter and authority in Turkic tradition. (Coin 7)

Crescent moon. The crescent moon appears exclusively on Type 1 coins of the Khaganate, where it is depicted on the reverse side, alongside the image of the ruler on horseback. On the left side of the coin, inscriptions such as "Khagani Turk" are rendered in Sogdian script. While the crescent moon motif is also present on Khakhanid coins, variations exist; some feature a star above the crescent, while others depict the star below it. This symbolic representation conveys themes of life, eternal prosperity, completeness, and perfection among the Inner Asian nomadic peoples. (Coin 8)

Huma bird. This imagery appears on Type 1 khagan coins, featuring a bird with outstretched wings alongside the khagan, who is seated on a zoomorphic throne. The reverse side of the coin displays a visible stamp, surrounded by the inscription "Tun jabgu-khakan" in Sogdian script. In the ancient Turkic ideology of statehood, "Umay" represents a specific deity, believed to be bestowed by "Tangri" (God) to provide guidance in state governance and to confer power upon the future ruler. (Coin 9)

Geruda bird. This imagery is found on Type 1 khagan coins, which depict a bird with outstretched wings adjacent to the khagan seated upon a zoomorphic throne. The reverse side features a prominent stamp, encircled by the inscription "Tun jabgu-khakan" rendered in Sogdian script. Within the ancient Turkic ideology of statehood, "Umay" is recognized as a specific deity, believed to be granted by "Tangri" (God) to offer guidance in governance and to bestow power upon the future ruler. (Coin 10)

Zoomorphic throne design. In three types of coins from the Western Turkic Khanate, the ruler (yabgu or khagan) is depicted seated on a zoomorphic throne. Notably, Zemarch, a Byzantine envoy to Istami Yabgu and one of the founders of the Western Turkic Khanate, reported that the khagan sat upon a throne shaped like a peacock. Among the numerous valuable artifacts discovered in the Eleke tomb monument in Eastern Kazakhstan, which are believed to be associated with the rulers of the Turkic Khaganate, gold belt ornaments were found, two of which portray the ruler seated on a throne in the form of a horse, facing both sides. Samashev interprets these findings as symbolic attributes representing the power of the Turkic khagans. (Coin 11)

Sword. The Ashina clan, engaged in metallurgy, produced swords as their first weapons. The processes of sacrifice and prayer were intimately connected to the sword, with one spirit even bearing the name "Sword." Furthermore, sword imagery is commonly found on balbals, the stone sculptures placed near ancient Turkic tombstones. These statues often depict figures holding a sword or displaying both a long and a short sword at their belts, underscoring the weapon's cultural and spiritual significance. (Coin 12)

Crescent moon and full moon. Unlike other coins from the Western Turkic Khanate, this particular type features a sun symbol resembling a full moon positioned atop the horse. This imagery is also utilized as a greeting symbol on the flags and coats of arms of the Mongols today. In the context of Inner Asian nomadic cultures, this symbol signifies life, eternal prosperity, completeness, and perfection. Furthermore, astral symbols representing the Moon and the Sun begin to appear in the visual arts of Sugd and Khorezm, where they are associated with the four-armed goddess Nana.

Cross symbol. Several types of coins from the Western Turkic Khanate feature the symbol of the cross.

The prevalence of the cross in the visual arts of Central Asia aligns with the early Middle Ages, a period during which Christianity began to gain a foothold in the region. This may be attributed to the alliance between Byzantium and the Turkic khanate, as well as the establishment of Christian communities in various cities. Such developments likely influenced the political landscape and ideological framework of the ruling elite during this time.

Camel with two humps. This imagery is present on only one type of coin from the Western Khaganate, specifically corresponding to the third phase known as the "Khagan period." The inscription "farn bagi khagan" (Godly Qut (owner) khagan) is rendered in Sogdian script. Additionally, this image appears on two types of coins from Bukhara, which are believed to originate from Poykent. In Turkic mythology, the camel, like several other animals, symbolizes "alpine." Notably, the male camel, referred to as "bogra," is regarded as a "symbolic power" by heroes within this tradition.

Discussion. An analysis was conducted of numismatic materials found in existing scientific literature alongside historical data. This examination addressed every symbolic representation of statehood, power, and ideological significance present on the coins. Currently, in Central Asia, there is a lack of dedicated expeditions for the study of numismatic objects, and there are relatively few scholars specializing in ancient Iranian languages (such as Sogdian, Khorezmian, and Bactrian). This deficiency presents a significant obstacle to bridging the gap in early medieval numismatics, thereby hindering efforts to illuminate the history and statehood of the region's peoples.

Conclusion: Fundamental changes were observed in the cultural landscape of the Western Turkic Khanate, where elements of theism, Zoroastrianism, long-standing local religions, Christianity, and Buddhism are reflected in the coins minted during this period. These diverse religious influences suggest that religious tolerance was a prevailing characteristic of the Turkic khanate, with rulers actively patronizing various faiths. Additionally, animals that served as totems for the ruling dynasty—such as the lion, horse, camel, and eagle (humo)—became symbols of authority. Astrological symbols, including the half and full moon and five- and eight-pointed stars, were also prevalent. Furthermore, symbols of power, such as zoomorphic thrones, crowns, three-pointed headdresses, scepters, and ceremonial attire, demonstrate a connection to the traditions of nomadic statehood. The resemblance between human depictions on palace wall paintings and ceramics from that era, alongside the imagery on the coins, underscores this relationship.

References

1. Бабаяров Г.Б. Древнетюркские монеты Чачского оазиса. – Ташкент, 2007. – С. 9-23.
2. Ртвеладзе Э. В. История и нумизматика Чача (вторая половина III – середина VIII в. н. э.). – Ташкент, 2006. – С. 88-97;
3. Шагалов В.Д., Кузнецов А. В. Каталог монет Чача III–VIII вв. – Ташкент, 2006;
4. Babayarov G, Kubatin A. Byzantine impact on the iconography of Western Turkic coinage // *Acta Orientalia Academiae Scientiarum Hung.* Volume 66 (1). – Budapest, 2013. – P. 47–58.
5. Çolak M. Türkçenin söz varlığında “Kılıç” // *Uluslararası Türkçe Edebiyat Kültür Eğitim Dergisi*, 7(4), 2018. – S. 2158.
6. Баратова Л. С. Византийско-согдийско-тюркский симбиоз на монетах Средней Азии // *Second International Congress on Turkic Civilization, Bishkek, October 4-6, 2004.* – Bishkek, 2005. – С. 419.
7. Альбаум Л. И. Живопись Афрасиаба. – Ташкент: Фан, 1975. – С. 32.
8. Çal H. Orhun Anıtları 2000 yıl kazısı: Karakuş tasvirli Sembolik Lahit // XIV. Türk Tarih Kongresi. Kongreye sunulan bildiriler, III. Cilt. – Ankara, 2005. – S. 525, 538.
9. Самашев З. Образ тюркского кагана в торевтике малых форм (по материалам культово – поминального комплекса Елеке сазы в Восточном Казахстане) // *Theory and Practice of Archaeological Research*, 2022 • 34 (4). – С. 163-190.

10. Сулейманов Р. Х. Древний Нахшаб. – С. 290.
11. Мусакаева А. А. Монета с изображением верблюда из коллекции Музея истории народов Узбекистана // Творческое наследие народов Средней Азии в памятниках искусства и архитектуры. – Ташкент, 1985